

FACTSHEET #FS2.1-06

Runoff harvesting with
field-side swales for
water catchment and
irrigation

//01. QUICK FACTS

TECHNOLOGY TYPE

Runoff harvesting swales

INPUTS

Landscape shaping; gravel; vegetation; precipitation and surface runoff from adjacent fields

OUTPUTS

Collected and stored surface runoff water for irrigation

INDICATIVE MATURITY LEVEL

TRL 7

CONTEXT & SCALE

Application in fields; suitable for arable crops (e.g. maize, cereals, oilseeds); adaptable to different operational scales, including individual farms and cooperatives

KEY BENEFITS

Reuse of rainfall and runoff for irrigation; reduction of uncontrolled runoff; reduction of soil erosion; improved drought resilience and yield stability; reduced dependence on fresh- and groundwater sources

KEY LIMITATIONS

Storage capacity; space; safety requirements for open retention; connection to an existing irrigation system

CATEGORY

Rainwater

//02. WHAT IT IS

Field-side swales for runoff harvesting are shallow linear surface water interception structures designed to capture rainfall runoff from cropped fields, filter through gravel, and convey it into a retention pond. The stored water is then reused for supplementary irrigation during critical crop growth stages. The system integrates simple hy-

draulic elements such as swales, sediment traps, a retention pond, and a connection to a regular irrigation system. This way, it offers a compact, multifunctional water management solution that reduces runoff losses and associated damages and improves on-farm water availability.

//03. WHY IT MATTERS

In temperate continental regions, rainfall is often moderate but highly variable, with summer droughts coinciding with peak crop water demand. Despite sufficient annual precipitation, crops frequently experience drought stress due to uneven rainfall distribution, as well as rapid heavy showers, with uncontrolled runoff and flooding.

This solution addresses water scarcity, erosion, and nutrient loss by capturing excess runoff during rainfall events and reallocating it efficiently during periods of need. It supports climate adaptation, stabilizes yields, and improves overall water-use efficiency.

//04. DESIGN AND SIZING

The system is usually designed as a linear retention basin at the edge of the field, running parallel to the cultivation area and connected to the field via a shallow inflow swale (up to 50 cm deep). The field-side swale incorporates a sediment trap and gravel filter to reduce sedimentation and safeguard water quality. The retention basins are U-shaped, shallow, and dimensioned variably in width and depth according to field size, available space, and typical rainfall volumes. The shallow depth also serves safety purposes, ensures low

excavation costs, and facilitates maintenance. An overflow channel safely drains excess water during extreme rainfall, preventing erosion and flooding. Sediments transported with runoff are retained within the sediment trap and retention basin. The stored water is redistributed via a small pumping system connected to the field irrigation system. The design parameters are adapted to local rainfall patterns, soil conditions, and plant water requirements to ensure efficient drainage and reuse of the rainwater.

//05. HOW IT WORKS

During rainfall events, surface runoff from the field is intercepted by the field-side swale and directed into a retention pond. Flow velocity is reduced, allowing sediments to settle to improve water quality.

During drought-sensitive growth stages or whenever need arises, stored water can be pumped to the irrigation system, providing a timely supplementary water source.

//06. OPERATION, MAINTENANCE AND MONITORING

The system requires low maintenance once established. Routine tasks include periodic inspection of swales and pond embankments, removal of accumulated sediment from traps, and maintenance of pumps and pipes. Monitoring pond water levels,

soil moisture, and filtration performance support efficient operation and long-term system reliability. Pump operation can be manual or automated, depending on system configuration.

//07. RISKS & MITIGATION

Potential risks include sediment accumulation/clogging, water quality degradation, pump failure, and regulatory constraints. These can be mitigated through sediment removal from the traps, vegetated buffers, controlled overflow structures, and regular maintenance.

Open water can be a dangerous trap for animals and especially children, so embankments should not be steep and slippery.

//08. GOOD FIT FOR

This solution is well suited for arable farming systems and orchards exposed to seasonal droughts and rainfall variability. It provides a scalable and cost-effective irrigation design that can be replicated at farm or cooperative level on different scales across

similar agro-climatic regions, supporting improved water-use efficiency and climate resilience. Within the GEORGIA project, the solution is implemented at the [PPK BRASHLEN cooperative for grain production on gently sloping terrain in northern Bulgaria](#).

//09. KEYWORDS

Rainwater harvesting; Field-side swales; Rainwater retention pond; Irrigation buffering; Water runoff and erosion reduction

For more information visit: [GEORGIA EU Project](#)

//10. FURTHER READING RESOURCES

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